

FINANCIAL DEEPENING, POVERTY REDUCTION AND FINANCIAL INCLUSION IN NIGERIA: ANY HOPE FOR DOMESTIC CAPITAL?

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Abstract

The goal of financial deepening is to expand the monetary band and ensure that as much as possible, monetary transactions happen within the ambit of the monetary authorities. This is all in a bid to ensure that funds are properly and adequately channelled to where they are needed most. In most developing economies, the informal sector is still in the majority with elements ravaged by poverty and financial exclusion. Therefore, until financial inclusion is achieved, financial deepening efforts cannot be productive. Guided by the finance-led, demand-following and financial liberalization hypotheses, we employed the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips Peron (PP) tests to check the unit root properties of our variables. The Auto-regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) was employed for the short run and long run estimation while Granger causality test was conducted on the Toda Yamamoto VAR model to determine the direction of causality among our variables. Based on our result, we conclude that the Automated Teller machine (ATM) model presents the best relationship between financial deepening, poverty reduction

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(household consumption) and domestic capital (gross fixed capital formation). Financial deepening and financial inclusion activities have also resulted in a decline in domestic capital. Poverty reduction (household consumption) presents a ray of hope for capital formation in Nigeria. In all, the causal relationship in each of the models exhibits a finance-led path for poverty reduction while the ATM model exhibits a finance-led path for capital formation, poverty reduction and financial inclusion. Therefore, development and investment policies geared toward poverty reduction and capital accumulation can rely on ATM transactions as an effective tool.

Keywords: *Monetary Transactions, Finance-Led, Payment Channel, Household Consumption, Savings*

1.0 Introduction

In any economy of the world, the pivotal role played by the financial system remains sacrosanct. Therefore, national governments will always strive to promote financial development in order to generate economic efficiency (Cihak, Dermirguc-Kunt, Feyen & Levine 2013; Lynch 1996). Financial development as a concept refers to the measurement of the performance of the financial system using some selected indicators that cuts across the money and capital markets. For the purpose of analysis, financial development is further divided into; financial deepening and financial inclusion, even though there has been a lot of confusion and mix up in their terms of reference in literature.

Financial deepening also known as financial depth is defined as the increased provision of broad ranged financial services to all levels of the society. This explains why monetary and credit aggregates used for measuring financial deepening are weighted

in proportion to the gross domestic capital. An effective financial deepening is expected to result in financial liquidity which can lead to increased business opportunities, increased economic growth and improvement in the well-being of the society. On the other hand, financial inclusion also known as inclusive financing has been tagged as the panacea for eradicating poverty (Cull, Dermirguc-kunt & Lyman, 2012; United Nations, 2017).

The focus in financial inclusion is the extent to which financial services are available, accessible and used by the widest spectrum of the population. Where financial deepening is low, it results in financial fragmentation which is characterized by financial exclusion. Financial inclusion will help overcome financial fragmentation and exclusion and generally foster productivity and economic growth (Debroy, 2010).

Essentially, financial inclusion facilitates both credit and savings for households. Access to and use of other financial services apart from credit; such as payments and savings have been described as even more important (Beck, Peria, Obstfield, Presbitero, 2018). Therefore, having an efficient, accessible and safe retail payment mechanism is crucial for achieving a higher level of financial inclusion. Financial inclusion via payment and savings channel also has the advantage of making government sponsored social programs more cost effective and efficient (Muralidharan & Sukhtankar, 2016). No doubt, financial deepening and financial inclusion being the crux of the matter in financial development both play important roles in achieving economic growth by reducing poverty and inequality while maintaining financial stability and a reduction in systemic risk (Han & Melecky, 2013; Hannig & Jansen, 2010)

Dwelling on some important theoretical foundations of the relationship between finance and economic growth such as Schumpeter (1912), subsequent theoretical positions gives

credence to the importance, nature and characteristics of the relationship between finance and economic growth (De-Gregorio & Guidotti, 1995; Guiso, Sapienza & Zingales 2002; Rajan & Zingales, 1998). The finance-led growth also referred to as supply-leading argues that, finance contributes to economic growth via its propensity to increase the rate of capital accumulation coupled with the increased efficiency in the use of capital in the present and future. When the focus is on a low- or middle-income economy, the relative importance of improved efficiency of investments is even much more important (Beck, Dermirguc-kunt & Levine, 2007; Khaitan 2014). It is established that a strong nexus exists between financial deepening as a measure of financial development and economic growth in developing economies than in the developed ones (Acaravci, Ozturk & Acaravci, 2009; Cull, Dermirguc-kunt & Lyman, 2012). This is especially significant for the total factor productivity of growth. The platform created by the liquid stock market to trade ownership of financial assets and other productive innovations, enhances efficient resource allocation, savings, investment, physical capital formation and increased economic growth (Bruhn & Love, 2014; Khaitan, 2014).

In a country where developed financial sector, households, firms and the economy at large benefit, business opportunities and innovations are encouraged thereby increasing industrial competition and the growth of firms generally. The household has access to better and cheaper financial services for saving money and making payments. By creating an efficient and effective platform for transaction between households and firms, transaction cost is reduced thereby making asset accumulation and consumption smoothening possible. The finance-led theorists therefore strongly support the view of finance led-causal relationship between finance and economic growth (Levine 1991; Levine & Zervos, 1996; Shaw 1973).

Demand-following theorists have taken an opposing view that business activities spur banks to finance enterprises (Odhiambo 2007; Patrick 1966; Robinson 1952). Activities of the financial market are considered a lagged response to economic growth. Therefore, economic activity is expected to serve as a causal factor to financial development. The popular McKinnon and Shaw (1976) paradigm condemns the situation where government intervenes in the activities of the financial market by controlling the interest rate thereby resulting in financial repression. They particularly focused on the developing economies suggesting 'financial sector liberalization' as a solution to the fragmentation imposed on those economies by centralized decision making. Financial liberalization through the mechanisms of increased labour demand and increase in wages for the lower income groups reduce poverty and inequality. Bank deregulation that results in the opening of more bank branches especially in areas previously unbanked; tend to provide increased income opportunities for the locales. Deposit mobilisation and credit disbursement is facilitated in the rural areas and thus decreasing unemployment while giving better opportunities to existing business owners.

One of the many benefits accruing from a developed financial sector is financial stability along with the reduction in systemic risk (Khaitan 2014). How well this is achieved is determined by the wideness of the spectrum of the population that have access to financial services and how well government regulation and supervisory framework covers their economic and banking activities. When banks have greater access to deposits, it increases their funding base and strengthens their resilience to overcome financial stress. The most efficient mechanism for transmitting the effect of monetary policy remains interest rate and credit administration. Therefore, it is important that households and firms participate in credit markets which are sure means for

reducing systemic risk. Participation of households and firms in financial markets will also lead to greater efficiency of the financial intermediation process through the facilitation of increased domestic savings and investment cycles.

Literature is replete with studies on the relationship between finance and economic growth both from the developed (Acaravci et al. 2009; Bist 2018; King and Levine, 1993; Levine 1997) and developing economies, (Ngongang 2015; Ogwumike and Salisu, 2012; Osuji and Chigbu, 2012; Shittu 2012). Many of them have looked at the causal relationship between financial development and economic growth using monetary aggregates (Osuji and Chigbu 2012) credit aggregates (Bist 2018; Effiong 2017) or both as indicators of financial development (Ibrahim 2017; Ogunyiola 2013). In addition to both monetary and credit indicators of financial development, some have even included the capital market indicators (Ngongang 2015; Ogwumike and Salisu, 2012) to establish either uni-directional or bi-directional causality from financial development to economic growth. Empirical evidences available also show that the direction of causality could flow from either finance to growth (Esso, 2010; Kargbo and Adamu, 2009), growth to finance (Gurgay et al. 2007; Ogunyiola 2013; Shahnoushi, Ebad, Daneshvar, Shokri, 2008), or bi-directional for different countries (Akinlo and Egbetunde 2010; Demetrades and Andrianova 2003; Odeniran and Udejaja 2010) or at different stages of development for a particular country (Chinaemerem & Chigbu 2012; Odhiambo 2009). However, finance does not directly lead to economic growth. Studies have shown that there is a transmission mechanism through which the effect gets to economic growth. King and Levine (1993a) argue that financial development stimulates economic growth by increasing the rate of capital accumulation. They went ahead to state four ways through which the financial sector affects growth. These include: fostering productivity improvement by choosing entrepreneurs and projects

that are of higher quality; mobilising external financing for the selected entrepreneurs; providing superior channels for diversifying the risk of innovative activities; and lastly, revealing more accurately, the potentially large profits associated with the uncertain business of innovation. This position is further clarified by Beck, Levine, & Loayza (2000) when they concluded that financial intermediaries exert a large positive impact on total factor productivity growth which serves as a transmission mechanism to overall GDP growth. Dermirguc-kunt (2006) sums it up by concluding that finance affects growth by influencing the saving, investment and technological innovations.

Another contentious issue in financial development and economic growth research is the composition of financial development itself. Financial development as a concept comprises of financial deepening and financial inclusion both of which could have varying effect on economic growth under different circumstances. In recent times, there have been a wave of agitations arising from countries with a large population of low-income households especially India on the separation of financial deepening from financial inclusion. Debroy (2010) argued that the two terms are quite distinct and the policy implications for the two differ too. When it comes to looking at the effect of the finance sector on economic growth, Khaitan (2014) adjudged that the term financial deepening is more precise and is able to give a better estimation of the direction of causality between finance and growth. Earlier, Mohan (2006) using some economic and monetary statistics of India, observed that financial inclusion is a serious concern among low-income households. Specifically, he observed that higher credit growth between the periods; 2001-2002 is not matched with a corresponding adequate deposit growth. He further argued that where deposit growth does not match with credit growth, the resulting excess demand would surely lead to increase in real

interest rate, thereby increasing the possibility of further financial exclusion.

Nigeria as a country with a large population of low-income households (Akinbode, Okeowo & Azeez, 2017; Anyawu 2005) have also adopted financial inclusion. This is evident from the policy directions and statistics given by the Central Bank of Nigeria which clearly spells out the financial inclusion and financial deepening activities. In recent times, there have been argument and heated debate about the rise in Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) that is not matched by majority of the peoples' standard of living. It therefore makes it important to dissect the term economic growth and begin to look at some investment and productive component. For the purpose of this work, we have identified capital formation which is a product of the savings and investment activities in the economy. This is to establish how financial development has affected this important factor necessary for economic growth. The result we believe will reveal the gap that may exist between financial development and economic growth in Nigeria. In addition, this study contributes to the on-going debate (arising from more recent evidences) on whether the expansion of the outreach of financial services have significant real effects or not, and if yes, through which channel? The rest of this paper is structured as follows; Section 2, methodology; Section 3, presentation of result and discussion of findings; Section 4, conclusion of the work

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Data & Instruments

The period of study covers 2009-2016. Our study period has been constrained to this time frame as a result of the condition of one of our parameters; financial inclusion. Data on financial inclusion indices with variants like ATM, POS, WEB transactions, Mobile Payments and Cheque only became published starting from 2009. Therefore, we collected monthly data on the transaction value aggregates of these variants from the Central Bank of Nigeria annual report (2009-2016). This was done to increase our observation points for a robust estimation and analysis. This constraint further affected our financial deepening parameter for which we proxy with the domestic credit. We take into cognisance the recent debate in the literature that private sector credit relative to GDP representing the credit aggregates may not be adequate. This is because credit is also provided to government.

There seems to be a consensus in the literature currently that domestic credit adequately captures the credit aggregates in the economy (Buncic & Melecky, 2014; Khaitan 2014; World Bank 2017; World Economic Forum 2012). However, because of our choice of monthly data and the impossibility of getting GDP monthly values, we have simply collected data from the Central Bank of Nigeria annual report (2009-2016) on the monthly aggregate domestic credit. Poverty reduction is proxied with household consumption. Household consumption has become a veritable indicator of poverty and inequality in recent times (BRAPOV, 2007).

Poverty and inequality estimates could differ significantly depending on the welfare measures and poverty line adopted. Generally, consumption and income serve as the yardstick for measuring welfare. However, in recent times, more argument and

justification have been put forward supporting consumption as a more accurate measure of welfare than income (Deaton, 2003; Meyer & Sullivan, 2003). Data on household consumption was sourced from the World Development Indicators (WDI, 2017) report. The annual data on household consumption was decomposed to monthly data using the quadratic data interpolation method.

2.2 Modelling and Estimation

For the purpose of estimating the relationship between the gross fixed capital formation, financial deepening, financial inclusion and poverty, we state a log linear empirical model as follows;

$$\ln GFCF_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \ln FDP_t + \beta_2 \ln HHC_t + \beta_3 \ln ATM_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

$$\ln GFCF_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \ln FDP_t + \beta_2 \ln HHC_t + \beta_3 \ln MBP_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

$$\ln GFCF_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \ln FDP_t + \beta_2 \ln HHC_t + \beta_3 \ln POS_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

$$\ln GFCF_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \ln FDP_t + \beta_2 \ln HHC_t + \beta_3 \ln CHQ_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

$$\ln GFCF_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \ln FDP_t + \beta_2 \ln HHC_t + \beta_3 \ln WEB_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (5)$$

Where, **ln** denotes the natural logarithm function, **GFCF** is Gross fixed Capital Formation, **FDP** is financial deepening, **HHC** is household consumption, **POS** is point of sale, **CHQ** is cheque, **WEB** is web transactions, ε_t is the error term. ATM, POS, MBP, CHQ and WEB are the financial inclusion variables. Since the five variants serve as alternatives within the financial inclusion framework in Nigeria, they are therefore modelled separately in order to check the significance of their effect on gross fixed capital formation. As established in previous works on payment channels

in Nigeria such as, Oyewole, Gambo, Abba & Onuh (2013), we also fear there may be auto-correlation issues amongst the variants.

3.0 Presentation of Result and Discussion of Findings

3.1 Preliminary Tests

We first tested for the presence of unit roots in our variables using the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and the Phillips peron (PP) test. The two tests involve the intercept and linear trend of the variables. The test statistics generated for the levels and first differences of the variables are given in the Table 1 below:

TABLE 1
TEST FOR UNIT ROOTS: LEVELS AND FIRST DIFFERENCE
OF VARIABLES

Augumented Dickey Fuller (ADF)			Phillips Peron (PP)		
Variable	Test Statistic	95% critical value	Variable	Test Statistic	95% critical value
LATM (level)	-2.462662	-3.457808	LATM (level)	-2.462662	-3.457808
LATM (f. diff)	-11.64273**	-3.458326	LATM (f. diff)	-11.64273**	-3.458326
LCHQ (level)	-2.462662	-3.457808	LCHQ (level)	-2.462662	-3.457808
LCHQ (f.diff)	-11.32092***	-3.458856	LCHQ (f.diff)	-11.64273**	-3.458326
LFDP (level)	-3.263787	-3.457808	LFDP (level)	-3.263787**	-3.457808
LFDP (f.diff)	-11.72701**	-3.458326	LFDP (f.diff)	-11.72701**	-3.458326
LGFCF (level)	-2.474226	-3.457808	LGFCF (level)	-2.474226	-3.457808
LGFCF (f.diff)	-10.08473**	-3.458326	LGFCF (f.diff)	-10.08473**	-3.458326

LHHC (level)	-1.289377	-3.458856	LHHC (level)	-11.91728**	-3.457808
LHHC (f.diff)	-6.539647**	-3.458856	LHHC (f.diff)	-6.977149**	-3.458326
LMPB (level)	-3.855574	-3.457808	LMPB (level)	-3.855574**	-3.457808
LMBP (f.diff)	-6.835594**	-3.459397	LMBP (f.diff)	-11.32311**	-3.458326
LPOS (level)	-5.207181**	-3.457808	LPOS (level)	-5.207181**	-3.457808
LPOS (f.diff)	-9.400661**	-3.458856	LPOS (f.diff)	-12.32421**	-3.458326
LWEB (level)	-4.206857*	-3.45708	LWEB (level)	-4.206857**	-3.457808
LWEB (f.diff)	-10.84660**	-3.458326	LWEB (f.diff)	-10.84660**	-3.458326

Source: Authors' Computation

N.B: 1%, 5% and 10% levels of significance are denoted as ***, **, * respectively. The asterisks indicate the rejection of the null hypothesis of unit root. All variables are in their natural log form.

3.2 Co-integration Test

In choosing our co-integration technique, we bore in mind the position of all the theories guiding the relationship between financial development, physical capital formation and economic growth. We therefore followed the works of Iheanacho (2016), Nwani and Bassey (2016), and Nkoro and Uko (2013) to employ the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) of Pesaran, Shin and Smith (2001), and its inherent bounds test to estimate the co-integrating relationships of our variables. Apart from revealing the magnitude of the lagged response of variables, this technique is also known to be suitable in situations where variables are not integrated of same order, or when they are integrated of either order $I(0)$ or $I(1)$ (Ogumike & Salisu, 2012). Our ARDL model is specified as follows:

$$\Delta \ln GFCF_t = \hat{\partial}_{0i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i} \Delta GFCF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{2i} \Delta \ln FDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{3i} \Delta \ln HHC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{4i} \Delta \ln ATM_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_1 \ln GFCF_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_2 \ln FDP_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_3 \ln HHC_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_4 \ln ATM_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{1t}$$

$$\Delta \ln GFCF_t = \hat{\partial}_{0i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i} \Delta GFCF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{2i} \Delta \ln FDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{3i} \Delta \ln HHC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{4i} \Delta \ln CHQ_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_1 \ln GFCF_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_2 \ln FDP_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_3 \ln HHC_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_4 \ln CHQ_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{1t}$$

$$\Delta \ln GFCF_t = \hat{\partial}_{0i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i} \Delta GFCF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{2i} \Delta \ln FDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{3i} \Delta \ln HHC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{4i} \Delta \ln POS_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_1 \ln GFCF_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_2 \ln FDP_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_3 \ln HHC_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_4 \ln POS_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{1t}$$

$$\Delta \ln GFCF_t = \hat{\partial}_{0i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i} \Delta GFCF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{2i} \Delta \ln FDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{3i} \Delta \ln HHC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{4i} \Delta \ln MBP_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_1 \ln GFCF_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_2 \ln FDP_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_3 \ln HHC_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_4 \ln MBP_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{1t}$$

$$\Delta \ln GFCF_t = \hat{\partial}_{0i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i} \Delta GFCF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{2i} \Delta \ln FDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{3i} \Delta \ln HHC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{4i} \Delta \ln WEB_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_1 \ln GFCF_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_2 \ln FDP_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_3 \ln HHC_{t-i} + \hat{\partial}_4 \ln WEB_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{1t}$$

Where $(\hat{\partial}_1 - \hat{\partial}_4)$ corresponds to the long run relationship, the null of non-existence of long run relationship between the variables is examined. This is defined by $(H_0 : \hat{\partial}_1 = \hat{\partial}_2 = \hat{\partial}_3 = \hat{\partial}_4 = 0)$. The decision to accept or reject H_0 is based on the following conditions: if F-value > upper bound, reject H_0 meaning variables are not co-integrated. On the other hand, if F value < lower bound, accept H_0 meaning variables are co-integrated. However, if F-value \geq lower bound and \leq upper bound, the decision will be inconclusive.

The ARDL model above is re-parameterized into the Error Correction Model (ECM). The ECM model incorporates both the long run and short run information. The model is specified below:

$$\Delta \ln GFCF_t = \partial_{0i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i} \Delta GFCF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{2i} \Delta \ln FDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{3i} \Delta \ln HHC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{4i} \Delta \ln ATM_{t-i} + \lambda_1 ECM_{t-1} + \mu_{1t}$$

$$\Delta \ln GFCF_t = \partial_{0i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i} \Delta GFCF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{2i} \Delta \ln FDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{3i} \Delta \ln HHC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{4i} \Delta \ln CHQ_{t-i} + \lambda_1 ECM_{t-1} + \mu_{1t}$$

$$\Delta \ln GFCF_t = \partial_{0i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i} \Delta GFCF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{2i} \Delta \ln FDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{3i} \Delta \ln HHC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{4i} \Delta \ln POS_{t-i} + \lambda_1 ECM_{t-1} + \mu_{1t}$$

$$\Delta \ln GFCF_t = \partial_{0i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i} \Delta GFCF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{2i} \Delta \ln FDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{3i} \Delta \ln HHC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{4i} \Delta \ln MBP_{t-i} + \lambda_1 ECM_{t-1} + \mu_{1t}$$

$$\Delta \ln GFCF_t = \partial_{0i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i} \Delta GFCF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{2i} \Delta \ln FDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{3i} \Delta \ln HHC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{4i} \Delta \ln WEB_{t-i} + \lambda_1 ECM_{t-1} + \mu_{1t}$$

Where $(\beta_1 - \beta_4)$ represents the short run dynamics. The Co-integration result is presented below:

TABLE 2
CO-INTEGRATION TEST RESULT

Models		F-Statistics	Remark
GCFC(GCFCIIFDP,HHC, ATM)	ARDL(1,2,1,1)	7.703408***	Co-integration
GCFC(GCFCIIFDP,HHC, CHQ)	ARDL(1,0,0,1)	4.213595**	Co-integration
GCFC(GCFCIIFDP,HHC, POS)	ARDL(1,0,0,0)	5.176912***	Co-integration
GFCF(GCFCIIFDP,HHC, MBP)	ARDL(1,0,1,0)	5.076733***	Co-integration
GFCF(GCFCIIFDP,HHC, WEB)	ARDL(1,0,1,1)	5.662724***	Co-integration

Source of Asymptotic critical values bounds- Pesaran et al. 2001
Selection based on Akaike information Criterion (AIC), Restricted intercept and no trend for k=3

As contained in Table 2, the result indicates that in all the models, the F-statistic is greater than the upper critical bound at 1% and 5% levels of significance. The null hypothesis of no co-integration is therefore rejected. The implication is that there is a long run causal relationship among the variables in all the models. The result of the long run and short run estimates of the co-efficient of our variables are presented below

TABLE 3
LONG RUN CO-EFFICIENT (DEPENDENT VARIABLE: GFCF)

Variables	ATM	CHQ	POS	MBP	WEB
C	-4.876283 (-0.913069)	-16.38089** (-2.458581)	-16.03137*** (-3.545889)	-5.466085 (-0.465537)	-2.117577 (-0.439213)
LATM	-0.166701* (-1.940425)				
LCHQ		-0.159738 (0.842882)			
LPOS			-0.103989* (-1.852815)		
LMBP				-0.028789 (-0.378348)	
LWEB					-0.108918* (-1.753608)
LFDP	-0.49889*** (2.683318)	0.432395 (1.567859)	0.630365*** (-2.66024)	0.375917 (1.253070)	0.418139*** (2.77131)
LHHC	0.473327** (2.389326)	0.872471*** (3.89972)	0.785193*** (-3.865918)	0.538584 (1.580960)	0.390192* (1.844850)

MODEL DIAGNOSTICS

AIC	-2.075899	-1.865592	-1.818013	-1.808309	-1.942698
SIC	-1.940617	-1.811826	-1.791130	-1.754543	-1.862049

Note: t-statistics in parenthesis, ***, **, * denotes 1%, 5%, 10%

The long run result presented in Table 3 above shows that all the financial inclusion variants are negatively related to gross fixed capital formation in the long run. Cheque and mobile payment have insignificant effects while ATM, POS and WEB are significant at 10%. The ATM, POS and WEB have significant negative effect of about sixteen percent (16%), ten percent (10%) and ten percent (10%) respectively on Gross fixed capital Formation (GFCF). The implication of this is that the productive economy is not yet benefiting from the financial transactions occurring from the usage of financial payment services.

In the review of meta-studies from low- and middle-income countries, Duvendack and Mader (2019) discovered that the impact of financial inclusion can be heterogenous across and within different levels of income, time, population, places, ethnicity and gender. They concluded that financial services may not even have a meaningful net positive effect on poor or low-income users.

Earlier, Cull, Hebreck & Hole, (2014) had concluded that most of the people using these financial services are not saving or investing. Recent high-level empirical evidences from developing economies (Barry 2018; Steinert, Zenker, Filipak, Movsisyan, Cluve, 2018;) and developed economies (Klapper and Singer, 2017) reveal that financial inclusion initiatives do not have transformative effects yet. Though positive effects could be

observed in some studies, Duvendack and Mader (2019) advice caution towards such. According to them, this may have been as a result of poor methodology with a high risk of bias. More rigorous studies with lower risk of bias are less likely to find any significant effect of financial inclusion.

Digital financial inclusion could have a negative effect on savings and investment except when it comes with some control measures (Ashraf, Karlan & Yin, 2010; Karlan, Ratan & Zinman, 2014). For instance, Karlan et al (2014) using Randomised Control Trials (RCT) conducted in Phillipines, Bolivia and Peru observed that digital text “goal-specific” savings also known as “commitment savings” helped the individuals increase their savings for housing, school fees and so on.

In another study carried out in Malawi, Brune, Gine, Goldberg and Yang (2013) discovered that the productivity of farmers was greatly improved when payment for cash crops sold was made directly into their savings account. The farmers involved in this practice also scaled up their investment in farm inputs by 13%. This in turn led to a 21% increase in value of crop output while household consumption after harvest was increased by 11%.

Earlier, Orszag and Orszag (2005) had recommended that workers in formal employment be made to sign up for retirement plan and other long-term entitlements linked to their savings accounts. This according to them will help overcome ‘under saving’ caused by inertia.

Schaner (2013) using a sample of women in Kenya, discovered that the reduction of transaction fees on ATM cards accompanied by a more convenient access to cash has a negative effect on women’s use of accounts. The study reveals that women with savings accounts are usually dissatisfied with the fact that they

have less control over withdrawals which may be influenced by their spouses. Therefore, such women will prefer savings accounts with controls and other security features just to ensure that they can accumulate more savings over time.

Financial deepening activities (aggregate domestic credit) and household consumption combined with each of the financial inclusion variants have also produced different effects. When combined with ATM, aggregate domestic credit has a significant negative effect to the tune of 49%, while household consumption has a significant positive effect of 47%. We can safely say that credit transactions via the ATM results in a decline in savings and investments. However, household consumption activities through the ATM channel boosts savings and investments in Nigeria. When there is access to ATM, households are driven to save more to smoothen their consumption in future but will save less when on loan (Barry 2018).

When financial deepening and household consumption are combined with cheque, aggregate credit has insignificant effect, while household consumption has a positive and significant effect of 87% on savings and investment. The implication is that household consumption going through cheque is most likely to be for investment. Under POS, aggregate credit has a significant and positive effect of 63%, while household consumption has a significant and positive effect of 78% on savings and investment. The implication is that both the credit and consumption transactions going through the POS contributes positively to savings and investments.

The insignificant positive effects of aggregate credit and household consumption under mobile payment imply the level of usage of this financial service is still very low. Under WEB payments, both aggregate credit and household consumption

have positive and significant effects of 41% and 39% respectively. The Implication is that credit and consumption transactions through the WEB contribute positively to savings and investment.

Evaluation of the models using the Akaike Information (AIC) and Swartz Information (SIC) reveals ATM model performs best followed by the WEB model. The model is best where AIC/SIC is minimized.

TABLE 4
SHORT RUN ERROR CORRECTION ESTIMATES
(DEPENDENT VARIABLE: GFCE)

Variables	ATM	CHQ	POS	MBP	WEB
ECM(-1)	-0.279290*** (-6.350560)	-0.209983*** (-4.691999)	-0.233503*** (-5.169299)	-0.248551*** (5.150195)	-0.269290*** (-5.440644)
ΔLATM	-0.276130*** (-5.406952)				
ΔLCHQ		-0.124137** (-2.715082)			
ΔLPOS					
ΔLMBP					
ΔLWEB					0.082518*** (-4.291416)
ΔLFDP	-0.4502777*** (-2.693904)				

$\Delta LHHC$	-1.119473** (-2.582336)			- 0.571339*** (-5.150195)	-0.718986** (-2.946813)
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DIAGNOSTIC TESTS

<i>Adj R²</i>	0.411103	0.242651	0.197477	0.198001	0.305997
D.W Statistics	2.230131	1.997176	2.049551	2.037896	2.121111
LB(Q-2)	2.0127	0.2376	0.5142	0.3724	0.7035
LB(Q ² - 2)	0.3026	0.0400	0.0390	0.0220	0.0551
Heteroskadasticity (F-stat)	0.141178	0.018847	0.017981	0.009679	0.025270
Ramsey Reset (F-stat)	3.504064*	5.006575**	1.187045	1.573175	0.123206

Note: t-statistics in parenthesis, ***, **, * denotes 1%, 5%, 10%

The error correction short run result presented in Table 4 above reveals the short run dynamics between our variables. Fundamentally as required, the speed of adjustment of short run disequilibrium in the long run is negative and less than unity. The diagnostics also conform to benchmarks. We observe the adjusted R-square is quite low. This we believe is as a result of the parsimonious nature of our parameters. Parameters had to be differenced at different lags to obtain favourable levels of significance. The short run coefficients are similar to the long run except that household consumption transaction via the ATM in the short run has a negative and significant effect on domestic capital. From the short and long run results, we can safely deduce that

ATM as a financial inclusion variant has had the strongest and most consistent relationship with financial deepening (aggregate domestic credit) and Poverty Reduction (Household consumption) to have the most significant effect on domestic capital (gross fixed capital formation).

3.3 Causality Tests

Going by the result of our stationarity tests where all of our variables are I(1) series with some also showing signs of significance at levels, in order to test their causality relationship, the Toda-Yamamoto long run causality test is found appropriate. Under the Toda and Yamamoto (1995) test, estimation is done on a vector autoregressive (VAR) model in levels. The method artificially augments the correct order of the VAR, k , by the maximum order of integration \hat{d}_{max} . This way, the usual test statistics for Granger causality has the convenient asymptotic distribution that supports established inferences. The result of the estimated model is presented below;

**TABLE 5
TODA YAMAMOTO (ADJUSTED GRANGER CAUSALITY)
RESULT**

	Null Hypothesis	Chi-square	P-value	Decision
ATM	LFDP does not granger cause GFCF	6.875044**	0.0321	Reject Null
	LFDP does not granger cause LHHC	7.051297**	0.0294	Reject Null
	LGFCF does not granger cause LATM	5.715090*	0.0574	
	LFDP does not granger	5.900958*	0.0523	Reject Null

	cause LATM				Reject Null
CHQ	LFDP does not granger cause LHHC	6..366781**	0.0414		Reject Null
	LCHQ does not granger cause LHHC	15.68210**	0.0004		Reject Null
	LFDP does not granger cause LCHQ	10.48755**	0.0053		Reject Null
MBP	LMBP does not granger cause LFDP	5.039875*	0.0805		Reject Null
	LFDP does not granger cause LHHC	5.506451*	0.0637		Reject Null
	LFDP does not granger cause LMBP	18.00334**	0.0001		Reject Null
POS	LFDP does not granger cause LHHC	5.550596*	0.0623		Reject Null
	LFDP does not granger cause LPOS	8.670692**	0.0131		Reject Null
WEB	No signs of causality	-	-		

The causality result presented above in table 5 shows financial deepening (aggregate credit) consistently causing household consumption in each of the models. This confirms the causal relationship already established between financial deepening or financial development and poverty reduction (Gazi, Muhammad, Mohamed and Teulon, 2013; Ogwumike and Salisu 2012). Again, under each of the models, financial deepening causes the financial inclusion variant (Sharma 2016) with a bi-directional

causality between financial deepening and mobile payment. Under the ATM model, financial deepening has the highest causality having uni-directional causality with domestic capital (GFCF), household consumption (HHC) and financial inclusion (ATM). We also observe causality flowing from domestic capital (GFCF) to ATM under this model.

4.0 Conclusion

Financial deepening and financial inclusion as components of financial development need to be separated. Our study confirms that both could have different effects on domestic capital (GFCF) at the same time. In the case of Nigeria, while financial inclusion under all the models has had negative effects, financial deepening has had mixed effects. Financial deepening and financial inclusion under the ATM model established to be the best have contributed to the decline in savings and investments within the period of study. The only hope for domestic capital is household consumption that has upturned from resulting in a major decline to contributing positively to domestic capital. In all, the causality flowing from financial deepening to domestic capital (GFCF), household consumption (HHC) and financial inclusion (ATM) under the ATM model makes a case for the finance- led capital formation.

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